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Design and Development of an Industrial Dust Suppression System for Mineral Processing Sites Laydown Areas

Mary Nena M. Faulve¹, Rolando Omambac², Renee C. Tan³, James M. Dumaguit⁴,
Rolan A. Sulima⁵, Arvin Mag-usara⁶

¹Caraga State University Cabadbaran Campus

¹Corresponding Email: mfaulve@ssct.edu.ph

¹ORCID Link: 0009-0008-0597-584X

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Abstract.

Mining generates dust particles and airborne dust, posing severe health risks not only to the neighboring community but also to employees. Laydown areas, which are not included in the existing mining misting parameters, experience dust problems. Traditional dust suppressors, such as water trucks, along hauling areas are not enough to prevent dust from reaching laydown areas and often consume excessive water. This study addresses these gaps by designing and developing an industrial dust suppression system that integrates innovative features, including misting, multi-stage air and water filtration, and a Faulve-Omambac Triggering Unit (FOTU), which traps dust before it escapes unfiltered. The findings from real-time data collection revealed a significant reduction in particulate matter (PM_{1.0}, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀) of 1.70 µg/m³ per minute within a 555.36-square-meter area, with statistical analysis confirming a significant difference ($p = 0.003$). Respondents rated the system highly in functionality, usability, and safety. Future work should include integrating protective housing, renewable energy sources, a built-in LED display panel, lighting, and continuous operational use.

Keywords: Dust Control System, Particulate Matter, Industrial Dust Suppression, Air Quality, Filtration System, Misting